

Removal of selenium from drinking water by adsorption

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Abstract : Selenium, a non-metal, is a member of chalcogen group which is a naturally occurring metalloid. It exists in +6, +4, 0 and -2 oxidation states. The permissible limit of selenium for drinking water is 0.05 mg/L (WHO guidelines) whereas; according to Bureau of Indian Standards the acceptable limit is 0.01 mg/L. The raw organic waste material (Sweet lime '*Citrus limetta*' juice residue) was used for adsorbent preparation for selenium removal from drinking water. The adsorbent prepared was characterized using SEM, EDS, FTIR and ZPC (Zero point charge). Batch adsorption process was used for optimization of adsorption parameters. Optimization study revealed maximum removal efficiency of 93.7% for selenium concentration of 0.1 mg/L for adsorbent dose of 0.05 g/50 ml Se solution having a contact time of 30 min, agitation speed : 650 RPM, pH : 4 and temperature : 313 K. After adsorption the EDS data showed the presence of selenium. The Temkin isotherm is the best fitted isotherm model indicating progressive saturation of the solid and also it indicated chemical adsorption.

Keywords : Selenium, batch adsorption, sweet lime juice residue, kinetics, isotherms.

I. Introduction

Selenium is quintessential at low concentrations but malignant at high concentrations. It is a basic nutrient for human and animal health (0.8–1.7 $\mu\text{mol/L}$), but can be lethal above 1.7 $\mu\text{mol/L}$. Thermal power plants, ore-smelting plants and oil refineries liberate selenium in the form of selenite and selenate. Considerable amounts of soluble selenium are present in industrial effluents. The main physico-chemical methods used mainly for removal of selenium are precipitation by chemicals, ion-exchange and by catalytic reduction. The chemical methods are costly¹. The permissible limit of selenium for drinking water is 0.05 mg/L² whereas; according to Bureau of Indian Standards the acceptable limit is 0.01 mg/L. It exists in oxidation states of +6, +4, 0 and -2 as selenides (Se^{2-}), elemental selenium (Se^0), selenites (Se^{4+}) and selenates (Se^{6+})². The oxidation states are the major feature of selenium chemistry that affects the movement and solubility of selenium in water. +6 oxidation state (selenates) are more soluble in water. According to EPA, finger

nail changes, damage to the peripheral nervous system, irritability and fatigue are caused by short-term exposure to selenium whereas long term or life time exposure exceeding MCL (Maximum Contaminant Level is 0.05 mg/L and 0.04 mg/L enforced by EPA and WHO respectively) causes finger nail and hair loss, dermatitis, damage to liver and kidney tissues and, the nervous and circulatory systems. By consuming selenium accumulator plant the syndromes "blind staggers" and "alkali disease" are being found in livestock. After chronic exposure to both inorganic and organic compounds of selenium, neurotoxicity (deterioration of motor neurons) might occur, leading to greater risk of occurrence of amyotrophic lateral-sclerosis. The long-term exposure to environmental selenium is difficult to assess for morbidity and toxicity³. The selenium can be removed by physical, chemical or bio treatment. Several technologies are used for removal of selenium at municipality level using activated-alumina adsorption, distillation, ion-exchange, reverse osmosis, coagulation and filtration, lime softening. Media filtra-

tion is a physical treatment that is being used; it can use simple sand filtration or can use membranes or ion exchange resins. The chemical treatment is done in three classes; precipitation, cementation and coagulation. Some other technologies for removal are activated carbon, algal assimilation, captive deionization process, electro-coagulation, enhanced evaporation system, nano-filtration, photo-reduction, Upflow Anaerobic Sludge Blanket (UASB) bioreactor, etc.⁴. Since the permissible limit for drinking water is 0.05 mg/L, most of the above mentioned technologies would turn out to be extremely expensive and ineffective; especially when Se (or any heavy metals) is in diluted form, which can be less profitable or can create environmental problems. So to mitigate their effects new method of adsorption is to be evaluated. Therefore, the adsorption by bio-waste (here sweet lime juice residue) has a minimal impact on the environment and is also cheap.

II. Materials and methods

A. Reagents

A selenium standard stock-solution of concentration 1000 ppm was prepared by mixing 1.4 g of selenium dioxide (SeO_2) in 1 liter (1000 mL) of double-distilled water. The potassium-iodide solution (2%) was prepared by mixing 2.0 g of KI in 100 mL of double-distilled water. 1 g of soluble starch was mixed with water and then added to 100 mL of boiling water and was constantly stirred. The starch solution was boiled for more than a minute and then it was cooled and used. A 2 M hydrochloric acid (38% assay) was prepared by dissolving 7.3 mL of hydrochloric acid to 100 mL of water⁵.

B. Preparation of sorbent

The sweet lime juice residue was collected from a local juice shop which was washed thoroughly with distilled water for removing dirt and traces of citric acid or any other impurities which might cause any hindrance in adsorption processes. Later it was dried in a hot-air oven for hours to remove any trace of moisture from it at a temperature of 80°C. The dried juice residue was then grinded to a fine powdered form and stored in an air-tight jar.

C. Analytical method

The residual selenium concentration in the clear aqueous solution obtained by filtration (using Qualigens filter papers 640 de; Code No. 88195) was analyzed colorimetrically. An equal portion of the solution containing 2–12 ppm of selenium was moved into a set of test tubes. An amount of 1 mL each of 2% potassium-iodide solution and 2 M hydrochloric acid (38%) was added simultaneously to it. The yellow color appearance which indicated the liberation of iodine was obtained by gently shaking the mixture; starch solution in a volume of 0.2 mL was added to it and then making up the volume to 10 mL with double distilled water. The optical density of the blue-colored solution was measured on a UV-Vis Spectrophotometer (Model UV 1800, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan) at 570 nm against the reagent blank⁵; according to the procedures outlined in the standard methods.

D. Experimental studies

The surface characteristics were analyzed before and after adsorption of selenium (0.1 mg L^{-1}) using Fourier transform infrared (FTIR) spectroscopy (IR-Prestige 21 FTIR spectrometer, Shimadzu Corporation, Japan), scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (JSM-6390LV Joel, Japan) and energy dispersive X-ray spectroscopy (EDS) (JSM-6390LV Joel, Japan). The IR spectra of the adsorbent were obtained by an FTIR spectrometer. For FTIR analysis finely grinded sample was taken and KBr disc method was used. A scanning electron microscope (SEM) was used for investigating the surface morphology of the adsorbent with 10 kV accelerating voltage for a resolution of 100x, 1000x and 2500x. The SEM was combined with an EDS detector which was used for analyzing the elemental composition of the adsorbent. A volume of 10 mL of 0.1 M KNO_3 solution was added into a series of 100 mL flasks. The pH value of the solution was adjusted from 2.0 to 10.0 initially by either adding 0.05 N HNO_3 or 0.1 N KOH. A mass of 0.5 g each of all the three adsorbents was added in each conical flask and without more ado was capped. The flasks were kept in an incubator shaker and shaken for 24 h it was shaken. The pH values of the overlying liquid were noted after 24h with the

help of multi-parameter probe. Thus, the zero point charge (ZPC) was determined by this.

Batch adsorption experiments were performed in conical flasks of 100 mL with 50 mL solutions containing selenium concentrations of 0.01, 0.02, 0.03, 0.04, 0.05, 0.1, 0.25, 0.50, 0.75, 1 and 1.5 mg L⁻¹. The adsorption mixture was agitated for a time period of 4 h using an incubator shaker with temperature set at 25 ± 3°C; agitation speed at 120 ± 3 RPM; adsorbent mass of 0.5 g; and pH of 8.4 as it was the resulting pH of the prepared solution by the distilled water. Analyzing the uptake of selenium from aqueous solution at different time intervals (5, 10, 15, 20, 25, 30, 35, 45, 60 and 90 min); the adsorption kinetics was determined. By adding various doses of the adsorbent (0.01, 0.02, 0.04, 0.05, 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.8, 1.0, 1.2, 1.4 and 1.5 g) to selenium solution having a concentration of 0.1 mg L⁻¹ (temperature : 25 ± 3°C; agitation speed : 120 ± 3 RPM; equilibrium contact time : 30 min; pH : 8.4); the isothermal studies to determine the adsorption capacity and intensity were carried out. At various pH values (ranged from 2 to 10), batch adsorption experiments were also performed by keeping all other experimental conditions constant (selenium concentration : 0.1 mg L⁻¹; temperature : 25 ± 3°C; agitation speed : 120 ± 3 RPM; adsorbent mass : 0.05 g; contact time : 30 min). The effect of temperature on selenium adsorption was evaluated in a temperature controlled incubator shaker at temperatures of 20, 22, 24, 25, 26, 28, 30, 32, 34, 36, 38, 40, 42, 44, 45, 46, 48 and 50°C (selenium concentration : 0.1 mg L⁻¹; agitation speed : 120 ± 3 RPM; adsorbent mass : 0.05 g; equilibrium contact time : 30 min; and pH : 8.4). By varying the RPM of the magnetic stirrer (Tarsons, 1115 watts Ceramic Spinot Digital Magnetic Stirrer Hot Plate, 6040) from a speed of 100, 125, 150, 250, 350, 450, 550, 650, 675, 700 and 750 RPM (selenium concentration : 0.1 mg L⁻¹; adsorbent mass : 0.05 g; temperature : 40 ± 3°C; equilibrium contact time : 30 min; pH : 8.4), the influence of agitation speed was studied. The influence of pH was determined by varying the pH of selenium stock in the range of 2, 4, 6, 8 and 10; and then the adsorption experiment was carried out on

the magnetic stirrer keeping all other parameters constant (initial concentration : 0.1 mg L⁻¹; adsorbent mass : 0.05 g, temperature : 40 ± 3°C; agitation speed : 650 RPM; contact time : 30 min). All the experiments were run in triplicate.

III. Results and discussion

A. Batch study

The selenium removal capacity q_c (mg g⁻¹) of the sweet lime juice residue powder was analyzed and calculated by contact time (30 min.) for a given initial concentration (0.1 mg L⁻¹) and at the best pH (4) by employing a 650 RPM agitation speed, i.e. 0.097 mg/g.

Fig. 1. Removal of selenium in optimized condition at different pH.

The ZPC (Fig. 2) study showed the value of 2.5, which is in the acidic range indicating the probability of adsorption of selenium.

Fig. 2. pH_{ZPC} of sweet lime juice residue

A.1. Removal under optimized conditions

On optimizing all the adsorption parameters, a batch adsorption experiment was carried out with sweet lime juice residue adsorbent in optimized conditions; i.e. having initial concentration of adsorbate of 0.1 mg/L at pH 4, with an adsorbent dose of 50

mg for a contact time of 30 min at a temperature of 40°C with a stirring rate of 650 RPM. Then the removal efficiency obtained was around 93.7% with a resulting pH of about 4.7 of the adsorbate. The SEM image after adsorption on comparison with the before adsorption image (Fig. 3a and 3b) shows that, on after sorption image the vacant sites are filled up forming a layer and a rough surface is observed, thus indicating the adsorption. Also, the EDS graph (Fig. 4a and 4b) shows the presence of selenium on the surface of sweet lime juice residue adsorbent which was not present before adsorption.

Fig. 3. SEM Image of sweet lime juice residue adsorbent : (a) before adsorption 1000x and (b) after adsorption 1000x.

(a)

(b)

Fig. 4. (a) EDS graph of sweet lime juice residue adsorbent before adsorption and (b) EDS graph of sweet lime juice residue after adsorption.

B. Isotherms and kinetics study

According to the calculated regression coefficients for the adsorption of selenium on sweet lime juice residue (Table 1), the data fitted reasonably well to the Temkin isotherm model, with a regression coefficient of 0.9021 (Fig. 5) which indicated chemisorption. An endothermic sorption process was indicated, as the sorption capacity increased with an increase in temperature⁶. The binding heterogeneity of surface and over a wide range of adsorbate concentrations are represented and predicted by the Temkin isotherm model. It is expressed as eq. (1) :

$$q_c = RT \ln (K_T C_e)/b \quad (1)$$

Eq. (1) is linearized as eq. (2) :

$$q_c = B_1 \ln K_T + B_1 \ln C_e \quad (2)$$

where,

$$B_1 = RT/b \quad (3)$$

where, T is the absolute temperature (Kelvin), B_1 is the heat of adsorption constant (eq. (3)), R denotes universal gas constant ($8.314 \text{ J mol}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and b is the constant for Temkin isotherm, and K_T (L min^{-1}) denotes the Temkin isotherm binding constant. According to the graph obtained from Temkin isotherm model, it is the 'L' isotherm. As the curve reached a strict asymptotic plateau, it testified that the solid had a limited adsorption capacity. It suggested a gradual saturation of the solid. The 'L' isotherm indicates that when the solute concentration increases, the ratio of the concentration of the compound left in the solution to the concentration adsorbed on the solid decreases; giving a concave curve (Fig. 5)⁷.

Table 1. Isothermal model fitting parameters for the adsorption of selenium on sweet lime juice residue

Freundlich isotherm		D-R isotherm	
K_f (mg^{-1})	0.03215	q_m (mg g^{-1})	0.0268
n (L mg^{-1}) ^{1/n}	1.2347	K	-2×10^{-8}
R^2	0.5665	E_s (kJ)	5
T (K)	298	R^2	0.5707
		T (K)	298
Langmuir isotherm		Temkin isotherm	
Q_m	0.0055	B_1	0.0055
K_a (L mg^{-1})	3.618	K_T	85.97
R^2	0.6966	R^2	0.9021
T (K)	298	T (K)	298

Fig. 5. Temkin isotherm for selenium adsorption on sweet lime juice residue adsorbent.

The adsorption data was studied with different kinetic models, namely the pseudo-first order model, pseudo-second order model and intra-particle diffusion model. The linear forms of these models were correlated to the kinetic data. The parameters with regression coefficient (R^2) for all the three models are listed in Table 2. The sorption process is a pseudo chemical reaction, as assumed by the pseudo-first order and second order kinetic models (eqs. (4) and (5)) and the adsorption rate can be determined, respectively by the first and second order rate constants^{8,9}.

$$\log (q_c - q_t) = \log q_c - (k_1/2.303)t \quad (4)$$

$$t/q_t = (1/k_2 q_2^2) + (1/q_2)t \quad (5)$$

where, q_c (mg/L) denotes the solute equilibrium concentration, q_t (mg/g) is the average solid-phase concentration of selenium, t (min) is the contact time, the pseudo-first and pseudo-second order rate constants are denoted by k_1 (L/min) and k_2 (g/mg/min) respectively. The calculated rate constants along with the regression coefficient (R^2) are depicted in Table 2. The intra-particle diffusion model explored the possibility of intra-particle diffusion. The basic assumption being that the film diffusion is negligible

Table 2. Example of Table 2			
Pseudo-first order kinetics		Pseudo-second order kinetics	
q_c (mg g ⁻¹)	0.00157	q_2 (mg g ⁻¹)	0.3006
K_1 (min ⁻¹)	0.083	K_2	0.0184
R^2	0.4924	R^2	0.9762
T (K)	298	T (K)	298
Intra-particle diffusion			
K_p (mg g ⁻¹ min ^{0.5})			0.0012
R^2			0.9562
T (K)			298

and the only rate controlling step is the intra-particle diffusion¹⁰. The model is expressed as eq. (6) :

$$q_t = k_p t^{0.5} + C \quad (6)$$

where, q_t is the intra-particle diffusion rate constant and it denotes the fraction of selenium removed (mg/g), k_p (mg/g/min^{0.5}) is the rate constant and t represents contact time (min) and C represents the intercept which gives the thickness of the boundary layer.

The best fit model was generated by the pseudo-second order model (Fig. 6a) with the adsorption data ($R^2 = 0.9762$). It clearly showed that selenium adsorption on the sweet lime juice residue was successfully described by pseudo-second order which suggests that the adsorption process might be chemisorption including ion exchange and electrostatic attraction¹¹. FTIR analysis of the adsorbent before and after adsorption also reveals that there is significant change in the peaks of functional groups, which also confirms chemical adsorption. The FTIR graphs of the sweet lime juice residue before and after adsorption are depicted in Fig. 7a and 7b. The aptness for use of intra-particle diffusion model (Fig. 6b) and

Fig. 6. (a) Pseudo-second order kinetics graph for selenium sorption on sweet lime juice residue and (b) intra-particle diffusion graph for selenium sorption on sweet lime juice residue.

Fig. 7. (a) FTIR graph of sweet lime juice residue before adsorption and (b) FTIR graph of sweet lime juice residue after adsorption.

the pseudo-second order kinetics suggests that adsorption process of selenium onto the sweet lime juice residue is rather a complex process involving both, the boundary-layer effect and the intra-particle diffusion, the ion exchange and the electrostatic attraction^{9,12}.

The increase in sorption capacity of sweet lime juice residue at high temperature may be due to enlargement of pore size or due to increase in the active surface for adsorption. This can also be possible due to the improved maneuverability of the metal ions from the bulk solution towards the sorbent surface and level of penetration in the sweet lime juice residue structure overcoming the rate of intra-particle diffusion⁶.

IV. Conclusion

SEM images showed possible adsorption sites

before adsorption which later got changed after adsorption as those sites were taken up by selenium. The EDS graphs also showed the presence of selenium after adsorption. The optimum concentration was 0.1 mg/L at an adsorbent dose of 50 mg/L, for a contact time of 30 min. The optimum temperature was at 40°C. The adsorption took place at an optimum pH of 4 with a stirring rate of 650 RPM. Temkin isotherm model was the best fit model. The process is endothermic which is indicated by the increase in sorption capacity with an increase in temperature. The application of pseudo-second order kinetics and intra-particle diffusion model were suggested by the kinetic study. The sorptive process is possibly a complex process involving; both intra-particle diffusion and boundary-layer effect, ion-exchange and electrostatic attraction.

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